

A Study of Relationship between Composite Strength and Mono-Filament Strength

M. Morita

Research and Development Center, Toshiba Corporation, 1 Komukai-Toshiba-cho, Saiwai-ku, Kawasaki 210, Japan

ABSTRACT

To confirm the accuracy of the so-called "Rule of Mixture", tensile tests of mono-filaments and composites were performed. Materials tested are glass fiber, Boron filament, HT carbon fiber and HM carbon fiber.

The tensile modulus of the mono-filament emerges completely in BFRP and GFRP, but not in CFRP. The tensile strength is a little different from the tensile modulus. In GFRP, the fiber strength calculated from composite strength is about 30 % higher than that obtained from mono-filament tests. On the other hand, in BFRP and CFRP, it comes up only to the level of 60~70 % of mono-filament test strength.

1. INTRODUCTION

The "Rule of Mixture" tells us that mechanical properties of uni-directionally reinforced fiber composite can be expressed by the following formulae,

$$E_c = E_f V_f + E_m (1 - V_f) \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma_c = \sigma_f V_f + \sigma_m (1 - \sigma_f) \quad (2)$$

where E , σ and V are Young's modulus, strength and volume fraction, respectively, and suffix c , f and m indicate composite, fiber and matrix, respectively.

To confirm the equations (1) and (2), tensile tests of mono-filaments and of their composites were performed.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Materials

Materials tested are glass fiber, Boron filament, high tensile strength carbon fiber and high modulus carbon fiber which are shown in Table 1. They have no surface treatment such as Silane or Borane coupling treatment except some binder for forming into bundles.

Table 1 Tested Fiber

materials	form of fiber	maker
Glass fiber	roving for FW 2052 filaments	A
Boron Filament	mono - filament	T
HT Carbon fiber	tow 40,000 filaments	T
HM Carbon fiber	filament 6,000 filaments	N

2.2 Testing Methods

Three kinds of tensile tests were performed. The first is the mono-filament test which is to clarify the scattering of the mechanical properties of the filaments themselves. The second is the dry roving test which is a test of a bundle without matrix resin (glass fiber only). And the last is a test of a composite of the above mentioned filament, tow or roving with an epoxy resin matrix.

A glass and a carbon mono-filament were mounted on thin paper frames with gauge lengths of 25, 50 and 100 mm. After each specimen was set on the testing machine, this frame was burned away. A Boron filament was also tested with various gauge lengths from 10 to 160 mm.

A dry roving made of glass fiber, that is, a bundle without matrix resin was tested, applying the method defined in ASTM D2347-67 with specially designed chucks.

One end of the fiber or roving composite with an epoxy resin matrix was also tested in tension. In the case of Boron, 550 filaments were bundled to form a specimen. Specimens were impregnated with resin in a vacuum, cured at 60°C for one hour and after-cured at 80°C for two hours. Resin used for the matrix was epoxy resin (Epikote #828) mixed with Piperizin hardener.

3. TEST RESULTS

The strength of the filaments varied with the gauge lengths tested. Figures 1 to 3 show the relationship of tensile strengths and gauge lengths of the Boron filaments, HT carbon fiber and HM carbon fiber, respectively. In every case, as the gauge lengths tested became larger, the tensile strengths of the specimen became weaker. For instance, while the mean strength of the Boron filament of 10 mm length was 427 kg/mm², that of 160 mm length was only 362 kg/mm². This is due to the increasing probability of defects in the filament.

The curve in Figure 4 shows the fracture probability of the glass fiber at a gauge length of 50 mm. The mean strength was 157 kg/mm² and Young's modulus was 7,540 kg/mm². There are two tendencies in this fracture probability curve. At the region of tensile strength of more than 100 kg/mm², the strength is under the control of inner micro defects. Below tensile strength of 100 kg/mm², it becomes suddenly weaker. This may be due to a flaw on the surface of the fiber.

Test results are listed in Table 2. Young's modulus are also shown there. Young's modulus of carbon fibers seems to be scattered more widely than that of glass fiber or Boron filaments.

The strengths of dry rovings are shown in Table 3. This is a little lower than the mean strength of the mono-filament due to the subsequent breaking off from the weakest one.

The mechanical properties of composites are shown in Table 4.

Fig. 1 Relationship between gauge length and tensile strength of Boron filament

Fig. 2 Relationship between gauge length and tensile strength of HT carbon fiber

Fig. 3 Relationship between gauge length and tensile strength of HM carbon fiber

Fig. 4 Fracture probability of glass fiber mono-filament (at a gauge length of 50mm)

Table 2 Mechanical properties of fibers obtained from mono-filament test

material	gauge length (mm)	number of tests	Young's modulus E_f (Kg/mm ²)		Tensile strength σ_f (Kg/mm ²)	
			average	s. deviation	average	s. deviation
Glass	50	79 (B)	7,510	715	164.6	27.1
	"	68 (C)	7,550	1,550	152.0	48.8
	"	41 (E ₁)	7,540	776	152.1	32.7
	"	19 (E ₂)	7,390	780	151.5	48.3
	Total		7,520		156.8	
Boron	10	35	39,100		427	36.9
	20	33	39,200		417	42.0
	40	39	39,400		394	40.5
	100	39	39,200		369	72.4
	160	40	39,700		362	51.9
HT carbon	25	109	19,500	3,720	225	46.3
	50	111	21,400	3,080	194	40.4
	100	104	23,500	3,010	173	39.4
HM carbon	25	109	31,000	5,030	209	50.3
	50	103	41,900	7,700	189	46.7
	100	105	50,000	7,500	170	41.3

Table 3 Test result of glass fiber rovings

Test No.	Youngs modulus (Kg/mm ²)	Tensile strength (Kg/mm ²)
1		106
2		100
3		103
4		114
5		104
6		105
7		120
8		118
9	6,610	105
10	6,050	121
average	6,300	109

Table 4 Test results of composites made from fibers shown in Table 1

gauge length		50 mm		100 mm		
average V_f	mechanical properties	Youngs modulus	Tensile strength	E_c	σ_c	
		E_c (Kg/mm ²)	σ_c (Kg/mm ²)	(Kg/mm ²)	(Kg/mm ²)	
	Glass	0.48	3,920	108	4,280	112
	Boron	0.18	—	—	6,980	42.5
	HT carbon	0.16	4,110	31.5	4,400	30.2
	HM carbon	0.53	20,700	59.3	21,100	68.5

4. DISCUSSION

Table 5 was compiled to compare the mechanical properties of the mono-filament, the dry roving and their composites with one another. Tensile modulus ($E_{f.comp}$) and tensile strength ($\sigma_{f.comp}$) of a fiber in a composite were calculated by solving eqs. (1) and (2) backwards, as shown in Table 5. A percentage comparison was made between $E_{f.comp}$ and the monofilament modulus (E_f) and between $\sigma_{f.comp}$ and the mono-filament strength (σ_f).

Table 5 Summary of the test results

fiber properties		Youngs modulus ($E_{f.comp}$) (Kg/mm ²)		Tensile strength ($\sigma_{f.comp}$) (Kg/mm ²)	
		50 mm	100 mm	50 mm	100 mm
Glass	monofilament roving (%)	7,540	6,300	157	109
	composite (%)	6,970 (92%)	7,640 (101%)	199 (127%)	207 (132%)
Boron	monofilament composite (%)	39,400	39,200 (99%)	394	369 (93%)
					250 (68%)
HT carbon	monofilament composite (%)	21,200	23,500 (111%)	192	172 (89%)
		14,200 (67%)	15,200 (65%)	109 (57%)	104 (60%)
HM carbon	monofilament composite (%)	41,900	50,000 (120%)	189	170 (89%)
		33,900 (81%)	34,600 (69%)	96 (51%)	111 (65%)

* $E_{f.comp}$ and $\sigma_{f.comp}$ of the composites were calculated from equations (1) and (2).

Young's modulus of the mono-filament shows up well in GFRP and BFRP, but not in CFRP. This is partly due to the scattering in the modulus of carbon fibers, and partly due to the difficulty of the mono-filament tests of carbon fiber.

The behaviour of tensile strengths of composites is a little different from that of tensile modulus. In GFRP, the strength of fiber in composites, calculated from equation (2), is about 30% higher than that obtained from mono-filament tests. But in BFRP and CFRP, it reaches only 60~70% of the mean strength of the mono-filament.

This may be because of the interface of the filament and matrix. Stress is well transmitted from the matrix to the filament in GFRP, but in the others it is not transmitted well.

The composite strengths are also affected by the properties of the matrix. Figure 5 shows examples of the relationship of varying curing time of the matrix and the composite strengths. If the matrix resin is insufficiently cured, the composite has only bundle strength (the same as dry roving), because stress is not transmitted to the filament by the matrix. And if the resin is

overcured, it becomes too brittle and cracks will rapidly spread across the fibers due to stress concentration.

In both cases, the composite has low strength. In this test, at nearly the same curing conditions, the composite strengths varied with different fiber materials. So, these phenomena are not due to the curing stage of the matrix resin, but due to the interface of the filament and matrix.

Fig.5 Tensile strengths change in fiber-epoxy composites with varying curing time

5. CONCLUSION

The relationship of the mechanical properties between the mono-filament and the composite was investigated. Materials tested were glass fiber, Boron filament, HT carbon fiber and HM carbon fiber.

Young's modulus of GFRP and BFRP can be calculated and designed from the value of the mono-filament.

As fiber strengths are affected by the gauge lengths tested, it is difficult to fix the value of tensile strengths of fiber in composite. Moreover, the composite strength is affected by the interface of the fiber and matrix, and the matrix resin properties, too. So it seems to be difficult to predict the composite strengths from mono-filament data.

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